

Independent Per-Phase Power Control in Four-Leg Virtual Synchronous Generators

Andrei Mihai Gross-Muresan, Milovan Majstorovic, Francisco Jesús Matas-Díaz, Goran Dobric, Manuel Barragán-Villarejo, José María Maza-Ortega

Abstract—Distribution grids are facing a great transformation in recent years with the advent of smart grid technologies. Particularly, more and more controllable devices, based on power electronics, are being deployed in this part of the power system. These interfacing devices are in charge of the active power management of many resources ranging from renewable energy sources to energy storage systems. For this reason, it has to be considered that power electronics may provide valuable ancillary services for improving the operation of distribution networks. With this regard, it is important to stress that low-voltage distribution systems and microgrids are by nature unbalanced due to single-phase loads. Consequently, the flexibility requirements and control capacities of converters interfacing distributed resources have to be greater with respect to those of balanced systems. This work proposes independent power control for each phase of a three-phase, four-wire virtual synchronous generator specially suited for these unbalanced environments. The technical feasibility of the control approach has been successfully validated through several Control Hardware-in-the-Loop tests analyzing both steady-state and transient responses as well as the performance on a microgrid scenario. In this last scenario, the performance of the proposal has been also compared to a virtual synchronous generator based on symmetric components decomposition.

Index Terms—Voltage Source Converters, distribution networks, microgrids, virtual synchronous generators, imbalance mitigation, single-phase control.

I. INTRODUCTION

The evolution of the power system over the last decades is a tangible proof of the society's commitment to achieve its decarbonization in the near future. For this purpose, the installed capacity of renewable energy sources is increasing year by year [1], modifying in a substantial manner the generation mix. Power electronics, mainly voltage source converters (VSCs), within photovoltaic (PV) or wind power parks are displacing electromechanical synchronous generators of conventional power plants. In the early days, when the presence of renewable energies was reduced, the operation of the power system was done in a conventional fashion relying on the regulation capacity of synchronous generators. In turn, renewable generation operated just injecting the available

primary power with their corresponding VSCs controlled in grid-following (GFL) mode. A GFL VSC behaves as a current source requiring to be synchronized with the grid voltage at its point of common coupling (PCC), normally using a Phase Lock Loop (PLL). However, the gradual penetration of renewables has forced this mode of operation to evolve to the present day, where renewable power parks must provide demanding ancillary services imposed by grid codes [2]. In fact, the technology shift is such that it is necessary to force inverter-based resources (IBRs) to behave as synchronous machines in order to secure the power system operation. With this regard, IBRs with controllers based on virtual synchronous generators (VSGs) [3] has been profusely analyzed in the last years for a wide range of applications: PV generation [4], wind generation [5], Flexible AC Transmission Systems (FACTS) with energy storage [6] and High Voltage DC (HVDC) transmission [7].

In spite of several implementations of VSG controllers can be found in the specialized literature, those that emulate the swing equation of a synchronous machine [8] or a similar dynamics through a proportional-integral (PI) controller [9] stand out. Despite the differences between these implementations, a common control structure underlies based on an outer and inner control loops (OCL and ICL respectively). The OCL is used to control the active power and reactive power or voltage for grid synchronization and generation of a virtual electromotive force. While, the ICL is usually composed of voltage and/or current control. Those VSGs with an ICL based on a voltage controller behave as controllable voltage sources and, therefore, may operate in grid-connected or islanded systems because of their grid-forming (GFM) capability. In contrast, VSGs with an ICL composed solely of current control behave as controllable current sources without GFM capability. The use of IBRs based on VSG control algorithms have a clear industrial application in microgrids, providing a technology breakthrough capable of reducing the use of diesel generators [10]. In fact, VSGs may contribute to fully unlock inverter-based microgrids with clear cost and environmental benefits [11].

In the particular case of low-voltage (LV) distribution grids and microgrids, it is of utmost importance to consider its inherent unbalance nature because of the presence of single-phase loads or generators. In fact, these single-phase assets generate voltage imbalance, which has to be controlled under the limits imposed by the power quality standards [12]. This situation has recently worsened due to an increase of domestic PV installations, which may lead to higher currents in the neutral wire and uncontrolled voltage imbalance [13]. This problem

Manuscript received XXXX. (Corresponding author: manuelbarragan@us.es.)

Andrei Mihai Gross-Muresan, Francisco Jesús Matas-Díaz, Manuel Barragán-Villarejo and José María Maza-Ortega are with the Department of Electrical Engineering, Universidad de Sevilla, 41004 Sevilla, Spain (e-mail: amihai@us.es; fmatas@us.es; manuelbarragan@us.es; jmmaza@us.es).

Milovan Majstorovic and Goran Dobric are with the School of Electrical Engineering, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia (e-mail: majstorovic@etf.bg.ac.rs; dobric@etf.bg.ac.rs).

has traditionally been tackled by implementing local control algorithms in the IBRs based on symmetrical components decomposition [14]. These approaches enable different control objectives depending on the IBR functionality. Different options have been proposed to mitigate the negative sequence including [15]: balanced positive sequence current control, constant active power control, constant reactive power control, negative sequence virtual impedance control, or negative sequence voltage control. With respect to the zero sequence, it is also possible to find different control objectives applied to three-phase four-wire (3P-4W) IBRs [16]: elimination of neutral current, reduction of the neutral current with fulfillment of voltage imbalance according to the grid codes, or balanced voltages at the cost of high circulation of neutral current.

More sophisticated system-level approaches with the aim of reducing the overall grid imbalance can be also found in the specialized literature. In [17], an improved droop-based control scheme was proposed for power sharing and control of islanded microgrids under balanced and unbalanced loads. In particular, a virtual impedance for precise power sharing with unequal line impedances and reduction of zero-sequence current was proposed. The results significantly reduce the voltage imbalance, the negative sequence power, and maintain the frequency within the standard permissible limit of 2.5%. A master-slave approach was proposed in [18] to collaboratively eliminate the negative- and zero-sequence voltage components in microgrids with several IBRs. These control strategies are, however, suboptimal since they do not consider all the available network information. To overcome this shortcoming, [19] proposed a centralized optimal power flow (OPF) algorithm with the objective of minimizing losses and improving the voltage profiles of LV networks. The proposed OPF was directly formulated in the phase domain, being computed the optimal per-phase active and reactive powers of 3P-4W IBRs. Therefore, this centralized control approach requires to equip IBRs with control algorithms able to track such independent per-phase power references. With this regard, [20] proposes this control strategy for 3P-4W IBRs operated in GFL mode. The reference currents were computed considering a steady-state formulation of the power terms, i.e. computed from RMS values and phase angle shift of currents and voltages. This approach has a good performance in steady state, but with a slow dynamics during transients. This shortcoming has been recently solved in [21], resorting to three phase-related virtual balanced three-phase systems. The virtual balanced three-phase technique is a possible alternative to control single-phase IBRs by applying techniques similar to those used in balanced three-phase applications [22]. This virtual system is achieved by generating a quadrature signal, i.e. delayed $\pi/2$ rad, to the single-phase voltage and current [23]. Nevertheless, operation in GFL mode might not be enough to guarantee the stability of networks with massive penetration of IBRs like microgrids. In this regard, seminal works [24]–[26] propose the use of cascaded voltage and current controllers for 3P-4W GFM IBRs based on the generation of three virtual systems using frequency adaptive second-order generalized integrators and PLLs. The proposal, however, does not incorporate any control loop to achieve an independent per-phase control of

active and reactive powers.

This paper extends the independent per-phase control presented in [21] to IBRs with VSG controllers, which has a clear industrial application to microgrids and with the following contributions with respect to the current state of the art:

- Closed-loop control of phase active and reactive powers of 3P-4W IBRs. The proposed control, unlike that proposed in [21], consists of a PI controller applied to the active and reactive error in each phase. This ensures adequate tracking of the references even in the presence of unbalanced voltages.
- Implementation of an independent VSG in each phase of the 3P-4W IBR. This allows independent inertial response per phase, adapting to load and generation variations in each phase.
- The proposed control structure brings VSG capability in each phase both in grid-connected and islanded microgrid. In the first case, active and reactive power reference setpoints can be assigned to each phase to minimize grid imbalance, as proposed in [19] and, simultaneously, provide inertial response and damping to the system. In the second case, power references per phase provided by primary frequency and voltage controllers may adapt the IBR operation to the microgrid load conditions.
- The proposed control structure providing the independent per-phase VSG capability is technology agnostic. This means that it can be applied to any other converter topology, e.g., three single-phase IBRs [27], one per phase, instead of the 3P-4W IBR considered in this work.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the implementation of the control strategy to achieve independent per-phase control for 3P-4W IBRs with VSG capability. Section III validates the proposal through the execution of Control Hardware-in-the-Loop (CHIL) tests in both steady-state and transient conditions. Furthermore, the performance of the proposal is compared to a VSG-based approach using symmetrical components for a microgrid operating under unbalanced conditions. Finally, section IV closes the paper with the main conclusions and future work.

II. INDEPENDENT ACTIVE AND REACTIVE CONTROL PER PHASE

This section proposes a control algorithm for the independent regulation of active and reactive power in each phase, in addition to the provision of VSG capacity to the 3P-4W IBR. In order to achieve the aforementioned objective, the algorithm consists of the following main stages, as illustrated schematically in Fig. 1:

- A. The generation of phase-related balanced virtual three-phase systems of the 3P-4W IBR. This enables each phase to be considered as an independent system.
- B. Implementation of a VSG control in each of the phase-related virtual three-phase systems, based on the VSG formulated in dq coordinates [9]. The main feature of this VSG implementation is that it allows for independent selection of damping and primary frequency response. This stage provides VSG capability to each phase of the

Fig. 1. Proposed strategy for independent power control per phase in VSG 3P-4W IBR.

3P-4W IBR. Nevertheless, it is important to highlight that the selection of this VSG does not preclude the use of any other VSG alternative formulation in the proposed control architecture.

- C. Computation of the real reference currents for each phase in the 3P-4W IBR from each of the virtual reference currents in dq coordinates. This stage transforms the virtual reference currents of each VSG into real reference currents for each phase of the 3P-4W IBR.
- D. Resonant current controller in $\alpha\beta n$ coordinates for tracking real phase reference currents.

The subsequent subsections provide a comprehensive overview of each of these stages.

A. Virtual Three-Phase System

The top of Fig. 1 represents a 3P-4W IBR with an LCL coupling filter. This device must impose different per-phase active and reactive power injections according to setpoints from a centralized controller. In case of balanced conditions, control of active and reactive power references is achieved by calculating current references in the $\alpha\beta$ or dq domains using an instantaneous power formulation [28]. However, this is not the case for unbalanced situations, since the instantaneous three-phase powers contain both constant and oscillating double-frequency terms. Consequently, establishing a correlation between the reference phase powers and the corresponding instantaneous power components required for the IBR current control poses a challenge in 3P-4W systems [29]. For this purpose, it is proposed to generate a balanced virtual three-phase system related to each phase m , $m \in \{a, b, c\}$, of the 3P-4W IBR to take advantage of the power formulation in balanced systems. To do this, the m -phase voltage and current are associated with their corresponding α component of a virtual $\alpha\beta$ stationary reference frame, while the counterpart

β component is obtained by delaying the α signal $\pi/2$ rad. This delay can be achieved in different ways [22], but this work has applied two cascaded low-pass filters tuned to the virtual angular frequency ω_{vsg}^m for the voltages and currents at the PCC:

$$v_{sm}^\alpha = v_{sm} ; v_{sm}^\beta = 2 \cdot \frac{\omega_{vsg}^m}{s + \omega_{vsg}^m} \cdot \frac{\omega_{vsg}^m}{s + \omega_{vsg}^m} v_{sm}^\alpha, \quad (1)$$

$$i_{sm}^\alpha = i_{sm} ; i_{sm}^\beta = 2 \cdot \frac{\omega_{vsg}^m}{s + \omega_{vsg}^m} \cdot \frac{\omega_{vsg}^m}{s + \omega_{vsg}^m} i_{sm}^\alpha. \quad (2)$$

The computation of ω_{vsg}^m used in these cascaded low-pass filters is detailed in the subsequent subsection. It is important to note that these v_{sm}^α and v_{sm}^β are equal in amplitude, but with a phase delay of $\pi/2$ rad, which is consistent with a balanced three-phase system. Consequently, the implementation of balanced active and reactive power control strategies can be applied in each phase.

B. Virtual Synchronous Generator per Phase

The VSG implemented in each phase is known as a synchronverter or PI-VSG [9], and consists of an active power loop (APCL) and a reactive power loop (RPCL) as shown in Fig. 2. The former is responsible for the VSG synchronization, achieved through the implementation of a PI controller applied to the active power error of each phase, $p_m^* - p_m$. The APCL provides the virtual angular speed, ω_{vsg}^m , and angle, θ_{vsg}^m , in each phase. The proportional and integral gains of the APCL provide the VSG with the desired damping and inertial response respectively [9]. In particular, the integral gain is computed as: $K_i^p = 1/(2H)$, where H represents the VSG inertia constant. The RPCL implements a PI controller on the reactive power error, $q_m^* - q_m$, to define the virtual electromotive force, e_m , in each phase. Note that p_m^* and q_m^* can be selected independently per phase. However, each phase itself behaves as if it were a balanced system thanks to the generation of the virtual per-phase three-phase system described in the previous section. This allows computing an instantaneous non-oscillating active and reactive power of each phase through the virtual $\alpha\beta$ coordinates as follows:

$$p_m = \frac{3}{2} (v_{sm}^\alpha i_{sm}^\alpha + v_{sm}^\beta i_{sm}^\beta), \quad (3)$$

$$q_m = \frac{3}{2} (v_{sm}^\beta i_{sm}^\alpha - v_{sm}^\alpha i_{sm}^\beta). \quad (4)$$

In addition, frequency and voltage primary controllers can be integrated in the APCL and RPCL of each phase to support frequency and voltage control of the network. The formulation of these controls is carried out as follows:

$$p_f^* = K_p^f \cdot (\omega_o - \omega_{vsg}^m), \quad (5)$$

$$q_v^* = K_p^v \cdot (V_o - V_{sm}), \quad (6)$$

where ω_o is the angular speed reference (typically 1 p.u.), V_o is the desired voltage reference (typically 1 p.u.), V_{sm} is the phase m PCC voltage, K_p^f and K_p^v are the droop constants of the frequency and voltage primary controllers respectively.

The VSG outputs are the virtual dq reference currents in each phase, i_{sm}^{dq*} , calculated from the corresponding e_m and

a dynamic virtual admittance, $G_v + jB_v$. The implementation of this dynamic virtual admittance is achieved using a low-pass filter (LPF) with a time constant τ . The conversion of the virtual references i_{sm}^{dq*} to real phase current references to control the 3P-4W IBR is described in the following subsection.

C. Current Reference Computation

Each three-phase virtual VSG generates the reference currents i_{sm}^{dq*} . Therefore, a total of six independent references $\{i_{sa}^{d*}, i_{sa}^{q*}, i_{sb}^{d*}, i_{sb}^{q*}, i_{sc}^{d*}, i_{sc}^{q*}\}$ are computed in the previous control stage. This means that the number of virtual references generated is greater than the number of independent real currents $\{i_{sa}, i_{sb}, i_{sc}\}$ to be controlled in the 3P-4W IBR. To address the imbalance between virtual and real references, the reference currents of the virtual systems must be transformed into those of the real one. To accomplish this, the transformation generated in subsection II-A must be reversed. This can be achieved by applying the Park antitransformation to each pair of reference currents i_{sm}^{dq*} to obtain their counterparts in the $\alpha\beta$ domain, $i_{sm}^{\alpha\beta*}$.

The next step in the conversion process involves assigning the reference current in the α component of each phase to its corresponding reference current in the abc domain $\{i_{sa}^*, i_{sb}^*, i_{sc}^*\}$. This process is analogous to that performed in (1)-(2) for voltages and currents, thereby converting the virtual reference currents into the actual ones of the real system:

$$i_{sa}^* = i_{sa}^{\alpha*} \quad i_{sb}^* = i_{sb}^{\alpha*} \quad i_{sc}^* = i_{sc}^{\alpha*}. \quad (7)$$

Note that the sum of currents, $i_{sa}^* + i_{sb}^* + i_{sc}^*$, may have any value since the active and reactive power references per phase p_m^* and q_m^* can be selected independently. The current balance is accomplished by the neutral current i_{sn} in the 3P-4W IBR and, consequently, the neutral reference current must fulfill:

$$i_{sn}^* = -(i_{sa}^* + i_{sb}^* + i_{sc}^*). \quad (8)$$

D. Current control in $\alpha\beta n$ domain

The actual reference currents computed in (7) in the abc domain can be converted to reference currents in the $\alpha\beta$ domain: $\{i_{s\alpha}^*, i_{s\beta}^*\}$, by applying the Clarke transformation. This reduces the number of controllers required to track the current references from three to two. The current references in $\alpha\beta$, together with the reference current i_{sn}^* of (8), are controlled by means of proportional-resonant controllers applied to the current errors [30]. This allows obtaining the PWM modulating signals in the $\alpha\beta$ domain, $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$, and η_n to operate the IBR neutral branch, as shown in Fig. 1. The last stage of the controller is to convert the modulating signals from the $\alpha\beta$ to the abc domain to operate each phase of the IBR.

III. CHIL RESULTS

This section is devoted to validate the proposed independent per-phase VSG control described in the above section using a CHIL platform provided by Typhoon HIL [31], [32]. A 3P-4W VSC with an LCL filter for phases abc and an inductor in the neutral wire is connected to a balanced 3P-4W LV voltage

source, as shown in the top of Fig. 1. This power plant is implemented in a Typhoon HIL101, whereas the controller is embedded in a LAUNCHXL-F28379D from Texas Instruments, which is connected through a TI LaunchPad Interface provided by Typhoon HIL. A picture of the setup is provided in Fig. 3 and the relevant system parameters and control gains are summarized in Tabs. I and II respectively. These values have been selected according to the methodology presented in [33], [34].

In order to evaluate the performance of the independent per-phase VSG control, four types of tests are performed:

- *Steady-state response.* The purpose of these tests is to evaluate the controller steady-state performance in different operating scenarios: *Test i)* balanced active and reactive power, i.e identical p_m^* and q_m^* per phase; *Test ii)* active and reactive power only commanded in phase b , i.e single-phase operation; *Test iii)* different active and reactive power in phases a and c and zero in phase b ; *Test iv)* control of per-phase powers when the 3P-4W IBR is connected to an unbalanced source voltage.
- *Transient response.* The objective of these tests is to evaluate the dynamic response and tracking of power references, as well as the degree of coupling between the powers of the different phases. The proposed evaluation consists of applying step changes to the active and reactive power references for different phases: *Test v)* single-phase active power step response in phase c ; *Test*

TABLE I
PARAMETERS OF THE 3P-4W VSC USED IN THE CHIL EXPERIMENTAL TESTS.

Parameter	Symbol	Value
VSC-side inductance	L_t	2.5 mH
VSC-side resistance	R_t	0.08 Ω
Grid-side inductance	L_s	2.5 mH
Grid-side resistance	R_s	0.08 Ω
Filter capacitance	C	1 μ F
Neutral inductance	L_n	5 mH
Neutral resistance	R_n	0.16 Ω
Rated power of the VSC	S_n	20 kVA
AC rated voltage of the VSC	U_n	400 V
DC rated voltage of the VSC	v_{dc}	750 V
VSC switching frequency	f_s	10 kHz
Grid voltage	v_s	400 V
Grid frequency	f	50 Hz

TABLE II
CONTROL GAINS USED IN THE CHIL EXPERIMENTAL TESTS.

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Virtual inertia constant 3P-4W IBR	H	5 s
Proportional gain APCL	K_p^p	0.015 p.u
Integral gain APCL	K_i^p	0.1 p.u
Proportional gain RPCL	K_p^q	0.1 p.u
Integral gain RPCL	K_i^q	25.0 p.u
Virtual conductance	G_v	0 p.u
Virtual susceptance	B_v	10 p.u
Time constant of virtual admittance LPF	τ	2.4 ms
Proportional gain of the current controller	K_p^i	10 V/A
Resonant gain of the current controller	K_r^i	400 V/A

Fig. 2. Block diagrams of the proposed per-phase PI-VSG.

Fig. 3. CHIL setup comprising a Typhoon HIL101 and a LAUNCHXL-F28379D.

vi) single-phase reactive power step response in phase a .

- **Inertial response.** These tests evaluate the inertial response of the independent per-phase VSG control. To achieve this, the LV grid voltage is varied with a rate of change of frequency (RoCoF) of -0.5 Hz/s during one second. Under this disturbance it is evaluated: *Test vii*), identical inertial response for all the phases; *Test viii*), different inertial response per phase, i.e. different H_m has been tuned for each phase.
- **Islanded operation.** This test demonstrates the ability of the independent per-phase VSG to synchronize with an islanded microgrid, provide an inertial response and damping, primary frequency and voltage responses as well as reduction of voltage imbalance through independent per-phase active and reactive power control. Furthermore, it is also included a comparison with an existing VSG control algorithm based on symmetrical components to mitigate PCC voltage imbalance [16].

A. Steady-State response

From *Test i*) to *Test iii*) a balanced ideal three-phase voltage source with a value of 230 V RMS and a frequency of 50

Hz is connected to the PCC. The steady-state phase currents of *Test i*) are shown in the top plot of Fig. 4. The setpoints defined for each phase are $p_m^* = 3$ kW and $q_m^* = -2$ kvar. It is observed that the currents are balanced, i.e. equal amplitude and a $2\pi/3$ rad phase shift. As a consequence, the current i_{sn} is null, as expected in a balanced system. Table III collects the filtered actual power values per phase after applying an exponential-moving-average filter with a cutoff frequency of 30 Hz. This filter shows the power related to the fundamental frequency, disregarding the power terms associated with the IBR switching frequency and the oscillation at twice the fundamental frequency. Therefore, these filtered power terms are denoted as P and Q , which are different from the instantaneous magnitudes p and q . The obtained values are consistent with the selected references, achieving zero steady-state error in the controller thanks to the integrators of the APCL and RPCL.

The IBR currents for the steady-state *Test ii*) are represented in the middle plot of Fig. 4. This test proposes a single-phase operation of the 3P-4W IBR, selecting only reference powers different from zero for phase b , in particular $p_b^* = 4$ kW and $q_b^* = 2$ kvar. As can be observed, the currents of phases a and c are null, while the current of phase b is not null and returns through the neutral wire. These results are consistent with the power values P_m and Q_m obtained in Table III for each phase.

The injected currents for the steady-state *Test iii*) are shown in the bottom plot of Fig. 4. The test under consideration evaluates the two-phase operation of the VSG 3P-4W IBR, with the following specific setpoints: $p_a^* = 2$ kW, $q_a^* = -3$ kvar, $p_b^* = 0$ kW, $q_b^* = 0$ kvar, $p_c^* = 1$ kW, $q_c^* = 3$ kvar. It is evident that the currents are only present in the phases a and c , being zero in phase b , according to the power references. The high level of imbalance causes a current circulation in the neutral wire, which is greater than the currents of phases a and c .

The powers of each phase are collected in Table III and indicate an adequate tracking of the selected power references. It is important to note that the controller performs in accordance with the specified setpoints, even in scenarios with significant power imbalance between the phases.

The steady-state *Test iv*) considers unbalanced grid voltages, particularly: $U_a = 0.95\angle 0^\circ$ p.u., $U_b = 1\angle 110^\circ$ p.u. and $U_c =$

Fig. 4. Injected currents $i_{s,abcn}$ of the VSG 3P-4W IBR in the steady-state response for *Test i*), *Test ii*) and *Test iii*). Conversion factor 1V/30A.

TABLE III
ACTIVE (KW) AND REACTIVE (KVAR) POWERS PER PHASE FOR THE STEADY-STATE RESPONSES.

Tests	P_a	Q_a	P_b	Q_b	P_c	Q_c
<i>Test i</i>)	3	-2	3	-2	3	-2
<i>Test ii</i>)	0	0	4	2	0	0
<i>Test iii</i>)	2	-3	0	0	1	3

1∠250° p.u., as observed in the top plot of Fig. 5.

Under this situation, it is proposed to operate the VSG 3P-4W IBR with balanced currents. To this end, the following reference powers are selected: $p_a^* = 1.9$ kW, $q_a^* = 1.9$ kvar, $p_b^* = 2$ kW, $q_b^* = 1.9$ kvar, $p_c^* = 2$ kW, $q_c^* = 2$ kvar, which guarantee the desired operation.

The bottom plot illustrates the resulting currents of this scenario, demonstrating adequate balanced phase currents and, consequently, almost zero current circulation through the neutral wire.

B. Transient response

These tests consist of performing a step change to the power references and evaluating the dynamic response of the VSG 3P-4W IBR. For this purpose, the following reference powers are initially established for each phase: $p_m^* = 2$ kW and $q_m^* = 2$ kvar, corresponding to a balanced operation. *Test v*) evaluates the step response at $t = 0.1$ s when the reference active power of phase c is increased from 2 to 4 kW. Fig.

Fig. 5. Steady-state response *Test iv*): Unbalanced supply voltage operation of the VSG 3P-4W VSC. Top plot: PCC Voltages $v_{s,abcn}$. Bottom plot: Injected currents $i_{s,abcn}$. Conversion factor 1V/240V.

Fig. 6. Transient response *Test v*): Active power reference change in phase c . Top plot: Active and reactive power filtered by phase. Bottom plot: Angular frequency of each phase.

6 represents the active and reactive powers and the virtual angular speed ω_{vsg}^m of each phase. This figure shows that the active power of phase c varies during the reference change, reaching the new reference power value with an underdamped second-order dynamic response. This response corresponds to the expected VSG response according to the proportional and integral gains set in the APCL [33]. It is noteworthy that the active and reactive powers of the other phases remain unaffected during the change of the active power reference of phase c . This implies a high decoupling in the control of

Fig. 7. Transient response *Test v*): Active power reference change in phase *c*. Top plot: Voltages at the PCC $v_{s,abcn}$. Bottom plot: Injected currents $i_{s,abcn}$.

the active power between phases. However, it can be noticed that the reactive power of phase *c* during the transient response is slightly affected, being rapidly corrected by the RPCL.

Drawing an analogy with a synchronous machine, the increase in the active power reference of phase *c* produces an increase of the mechanical power, which leads to a transient acceleration, i.e. increase of the angular speed which is later corrected before reaching a new steady-state regime. This phenomenon is clearly observed in the virtual angular speed ω_{vsg}^c , which increases with respect to its nominal value. This increase is corrected and returns to the nominal frequency when P_c reaches the new power setpoint. It is important to note that the virtual angular speed of the other phases remains unaltered, as their active power references are maintained constant. This decoupling between the phases is also clearly evidenced in the instantaneous voltages and currents shown in Fig. 7. During the reference change, only the currents of phase *c* and the neutral wire change. The latter adapts to the new state due to the change in the phase *c* reference. Both currents evolve with a dynamic response that is consistent with the power evolution. The currents of other two phases remain unchanged as is evident in the bottom plot of Fig. 7. The voltages remain unchanged since an ideal voltage source is connected to the PCC.

This result reinforces the high degree of decoupling between each of the PI-VSG implemented in the phases of the 3P-4W IBR.

The same starting point as the previous test is used in the *Test vi*). At $t = 0.1$ s, a step reference change to the reference reactive power of phase *a* to $q_a^* = -4$ kvar is commanded, transitioning from an injection to an absorption reactive power scenario. The transient response to this reference change is represented in Fig. 8. It is clearly observed that the reactive power of phase *a* reaches the new reactive power reference smoothly, similar to the response of a first-order system. This response is achieved thanks to the gain tuning of the RPCL. The powers of the other phases remain unchanged, once again indicating a high decoupling between the phase powers. In

Fig. 8. Transient response *Test vi*): Reactive power reference change in phase *a*. Top plot: Filtered per-phase active and reactive powers. Bottom plot: Angular frequency of each phase.

Fig. 9. Transient response *Test vi*): Reactive power reference change in phase *a*. Top plot: Voltages at the PCC $v_{s,abcn}$. Bottom plot: Injected currents $i_{s,abcn}$.

an analogous manner to the preceding *Test v*), only the active power associated with phase *a* is slightly altered. However, this disturbance is rapidly compensated by the APCL. With respect to the virtual angular speed of the three phases, it is observed that only the phase *a* is barely modified, whereas the phases *b* and *c* remain unperturbed. Nevertheless, this variation in the angular speed of phase *a* is quite reduced compared to the one of *Test v*). In fact, this variation is because of the transient response of the active power and not due to the change of the reactive power reference. Similar to the previous test, it

Fig. 10. Inertial response *Test vii*): RoCoF of -0.5 Hz/s with $H = 5$ s. Top plot: Filtered per-phase active and reactive powers. Bottom plot: Angular frequency of each phase.

Fig. 11. Inertial response *Test viii*): RoCoF of -0.5 Hz/s with $H_a = 10$ s, $H_b = 5$ s and $H_c = 15$ s. Top plot: Active and reactive power filtered by phase. Bottom plot: Angular frequency of each phase.

is observed that the only currents affected are those of phase a , associated to the reference change, and the neutral wire to adapt to the new operation scenario as shown in Fig. 9.

C. Inertial response test

Test vii) evaluates the inertial response of the PI-VSGs with identical H in each phase imposing a RoCoF of -0.5 Hz/s in the supply voltage.

Initially, the frequency is set to 50 Hz and the reference power for each phase is randomly selected with the following setpoints: $p_a^* = 2$ kW, $q_a^* = -2$ kvar, $p_b^* = 3$ kW, $q_b^* = 2$ kvar, $p_c^* = 1$ kW and $q_c^* = 0$ kvar. In this operational state, the frequency variation is activated at $t = 0.2$ s and maintained for 1 s. Consequently, a new constant frequency of 49.5 Hz is reached at $t = 1.2$ s, being maintained for the rest of the test.

The response of each phase in terms of power and angular speed is shown in Fig. 10. Initially, each phase adequately tracks its reference powers until the frequency variation occurs at 0.2 s. From that moment onwards, the active power of each phase increases until a new steady state is reached, which is maintained throughout the frequency disturbance. Once the frequency variation has ended and remains constant, the active power of each phase returns to its original reference. This power increase during frequency variation corresponds to the inertial response of each per-phase PI-VSG. The power increase observed in each phase is identical, approximately 0.667 kW. This results in a total increase in active power of 2 kW for the 3P-4W IBR. This value must be consistent with the total inertia constant H selected for the PI-VSG collected in Tab. II. According to the RoCoF value and the IBR base

power, the theoretical power related to the inertial response should be: $2 \cdot H \cdot RoCoF \cdot Sb = 2 \cdot 5 \cdot (0.5/50) \cdot 20 = 2$ kW, as obtained in the experimental CHIL results.

Regarding reactive power, it is observed that it remains unchanged during the frequency event, once more evidencing the high decoupling of the active and reactive power terms achieved by the controller during the inertial response.

The evolution of the virtual angular speed of each phase is shown in the bottom plot of Fig. 10. It can be seen that they all follow the same trend, since H and RoCoF are equal for all the phases. In addition, the virtual angular speed follows the imposed RoCoF voltage slightly modified by the dynamics of each per-phase PI-VSG.

Finally, *Test viii*) analyzes the performance in a frequency event, but with asymmetric per-phase inertia constants set to $H_a = 10$ s, $H_b = 5$ s and $H_c = 15$ s. In contrast to the symmetric inertial response shown in Fig. 10 for *Test vii*), the results for *Test viii*), presented in Fig. 11, exhibit a different active power increase in each phase. Specifically, the power increment in phase c during the RoCoF is the largest, followed by phase a , and then phase b ($\Delta p_c > \Delta p_a > \Delta p_b$), as expected according to the H values assigned to each phase. In fact, the power increment of phase c and a is three times and twice that of phase b in steady-state respectively. This difference in H is also reflected in the response speed of each phase, the higher H the slower the active power response of the VSG, emulating the behavior of a synchronous generator.

Fig. 12. Islanded operation. Microgrid composed of two VSCs and supplying balanced and unbalanced loads. Left side CGI is a grid-forming VSG named PI-OL and right side CGI corresponds to the per-phase VSG named UPI-CC.

D. Islanded operation

The performance of the per-phase VSG in islanded systems is tested in the microgrid shown in Fig. 12, which is composed of two IBRs connected across the two 3P-4W lines Z_{L1} and Z_{L2} , with parameters depicted in Table V, and two loads. The one connected to switch $K1$ is a balanced load that absorbs 6 kW and 1.5 kvar, while the one connected to $K2$ is a single-phase load (phase a to neutral) consuming 2 kW and 2 kvar. The left-side IBR, named PI-OL, corresponds to a GFM VSG composed of an OCL based on a PI controller, identical to those proposed in this work, and an ICL based on an open-loop voltage control. Therefore, this IBR has GFM and black-start capabilities. This PI-OL is controlled considering a balanced three-phase approach without any imbalance compensation. This IBR is connected to the microgrid with an LCL filter with the following parameters: 0.8 mH, 10 μ F, 0.8 mH, to guarantee adequate power quality of the microgrid voltages. In addition, the PI-OL is equipped with a primary frequency and voltage controllers for computing the active and reactive power references for the OCL. The primary frequency controller is implemented with the frequency error using the virtual angular speed of the GFM PI-OL. On the other hand, the primary voltage controller is formulated considering the error with respect to the RMS voltage at the PCC 1. Details of the PI-OL control algorithm can be found in [33], being the applied control gains collected in Table V. The IBR on the right-side of Fig. 12 corresponds to the proposed per-phase VSG, named as UPI-CC. Similarly to the PI-OL, a primary frequency and voltage controller are added to each phase. These are integrated in parallel with the active and reactive power references, p_m^* and q_m^* , in the per-phase VSG as shown in Fig. 2, being possible to be activated or deactivated according to the services provided by the UPI-CC.

TABLE IV
CONTROL GAINS OF THE GRID-FORMING PI-OL IBR AND PARAMETERS OF THE MICROGRID.

Parameter	Symbol	Value
Virtual inertia constant PI-OL IBR	H	5 s
Proportional gain APCL	K_p^p	0.0159 p.u
Integral gain APCL	K_i^p	1.0 p.u
Proportional gain RPCL	K_p^q	0.1 p.u
Integral gain RPCL	K_i^q	1.0 p.u
Frequency droop controller	K_p^f	20 p.u
Voltage droop controller	K_p^v	5 p.u
Line impedance 1	Z_{L1}	$0.100 + 0.063j \Omega$
Line impedance 2	Z_{L2}	$0.240 + 0.251j \Omega$

The experimental validation of the performance within an islanded microgrid has been carried out via a real-time co-simulation using two real-time control platforms: OPAL-RT 5600 and Typhoon HIL 101. The modeling and control of the UPI-CC is performed on Typhoon HIL 101, as shown in Fig. 3, while the rest of the microgrid and the control of the PI-OL are embedded in OPAL-RT. Both platforms exchange analog signals to create the microgrid. The voltage measured at the end of line 2 in OPAL-RT, v_{abcn} , is sent by the analog outputs (AO) to the analog inputs (AI) of Typhoon HIL, which imposes that voltage on PCC 2 of the UPI-CC. Meanwhile, the current injected by the UPI-CC in PCC 2, i_{abc} , is sent by the Typhoon HIL AOs to the OPAL-RT AIs to be injected at the end of line 2. It should be noted that the delay in the exchange of analog signals is 50 μ s, preventing closed-loop stability problems.

The microgrid operation and the events performed starting from the black start are explained below step by step:

- Event 1. The voltage level and frequency are imposed by the PI-OL because of its inherent GFM capability. Black start is performed in ramp mode increasing from 0 to 230 V in one second.
- Event 2. Once the grid is formed, the UPI-CC is synchronized with the microgrid created by the PI-OL. Initially, the per-phase active and reactive power references, p_m^* and q_m^* , from the secondary controller are null and the primary controllers are not activated.
- Event 3. The balanced three-phase load is then connected closing switch $K1$.
- Event 4. Next, the primary frequency and voltage controllers of the UPI-CC are activated. Note that the regulation constant for the primary loops and the nominal power of both VSGs have been selected identically.
- Event 5. Once the load has been shared between both VSGs, the single-phase load of phase a is connected closing switch $K2$, leading to an unbalance load scenario.
- Event 6. Finally, the UPI-CC power references of phase a , p_a^* and q_a^* , from the secondary controller are modified to supply the single-phase load added in the previous event.

Figure 13 shows the evolution of phase voltages and currents (RMS values), powers and virtual angular speeds in the PCCs of both VSGs. The left-side plots show the results recorded in OPAL-RT for the PI-OL and the right-side plots those recorded in Typhoon HIL for the UPI-CC. The figure also uses underlined numbers to indicate the time instant when each of the above described events occurs. The location of these numbers in each subplot highlights the impact that the event

Fig. 13. Real-time co-simulation results. Left side: PI-OL executed in OPAL-RT. Right side: UPI-CC executed in Typhoon HIL. Magnitudes from top to bottom: RMS voltages, RMS currents, three-phase instantaneous active and reactive powers (PI-OL)/active and reactive powers per-phase (UPI-CC) and virtual angular speeds.

has in the represented microgrid magnitudes. A description of the performance of each event can be found below:

- Event 1. Up to $t=1$ s, the voltage amplitude ramps to the nominal voltage. During this period, the angular speed undergoes a transient evolution until the voltage reaches its nominal value. The voltage and frequency shown for the UPI-CC are measured before its coupling, therefore, they corresponds to the voltage imposed by the PI-OL.
- Event 2. Once the voltage and frequency are at their nominal values, the UPI-CC is synchronized with the PI-OL. This process is really smooth since only a slight disturbance can be noticed in the UPI-CC currents. After that, the currents of both PI-OL and UPI-CC are zero since no load is connected.
- Event 3. Close to $t=15$ s, the balanced three-phase load

is connected. This load is powered solely by the PI-OL, since the UPI-CC has null power references and their primary frequency and voltage controllers are disabled. The load connection is clearly noticeable in the PI-OL, because of the increase of currents, instantaneous powers and angular speed drop. In contrast, the UPI-CC only exhibits a transient response when the load is connected, after which both currents and powers return to zero. This transient behavior is associated with the inertial response provided by the UPI-CC because of the frequency drop when the balanced load is connected. Note that the angular speeds of PI-OL and UPI-CC evolve similarly since they are synchronized.

- Event 4. Around $t = 25$ s, the UPI-CC primary controllers are activated and, as a consequence, load sharing between

Fig. 14. Real-time co-simulation results. Left side: PI-OL executed in OPAL-RT. Right side: PI-CC based on symmetrical components executed in Typhoon HIL. Magnitudes from top to bottom: RMS voltages per phase (PI-OL)/RMS voltages of the symmetrical components (PI-CC), RMS currents, three-phase instantaneous active and reactive powers (PI-OL)/active and reactive powers per-phase (PI-CC) and virtual angular speeds.

both IBRs is produced: the UPI-CC current increases while the PI-OL decreases till they reach the same value. This is because both VSGs have the same rated power and identical primary control gains. This effect can be also observed in the active and reactive powers. The load sharing between the two VSGs help to increase the system angular speed, as can be seen in the bottom plot of both VSGs.

- Event 5. The single-phase load is connected to phase a . The PI-OL injects most of the current demanded by this load increasing the phase a current and also the neutral wire current. This leads to an unbalanced PI-OL voltage since no control algorithms to mitigate the imbalance are in place. The zoomed area in the PI-OL voltages reflects the voltage imbalance, with a difference of almost 15

V between the voltages of phase a and b . Because of this, the PI-OL angular speed and powers contains 100-Hz oscillation terms, as shown in the zoomed area of the corresponding subplots. The zoomed area represents 100 ms to clearly identify 10 cycles of the 100-Hz oscillation. The UPI-CC phase currents are slightly increased due mainly to the action of the voltage primary controller which reacts independently in each phase. Reactive power is injected in phase a to increase this voltage, but in phase b reactive power is absorbed to reduce the phase voltage. This different control action also causes a neutral current circulation in the UPI-CC. Note that the UPI-CC angular speeds are not oscillatory due to the proposed control strategy. Each UPI-CC phase always observes a balanced system regardless of any existing microgrid imbalance.

- Event 6. The last event consists of setting the UPI-CC power references of phase a , p_a^* and q_a^* , equal to those demanded by the single-phase load, i.e. 2 kW and 2 kvar. The UPI-CC phase a and neutral currents increase due to this control, while the PI-OL phase a current decreases until a balanced operation is reached. This control action balances the grid-forming PI-OL operation by eliminating the need to assume the power of the unbalanced load from this IBR. This increases the angular speed of the microgrid and reduces oscillation of power terms and angular speed.

In order to compare the results obtained with other approaches in the literature, the performance of a VSG based on symmetric components decomposition [35] is evaluated on the IBR connected in PCC 2, which from now on will be referred as PI-CC. The positive sequence is controlled using the PI-VSG concept [9], with an ICL based on current control [33], while the negative- and zero-sequence voltages at the PCC are eliminated by applying resonant controllers tuned to the fundamental frequency, following the approach presented in [16]. Additionally, the primary frequency and voltage controllers are integrated to generate the active and reactive power references to the PI-CC as previously. Note that these controllers are formulated using the positive-sequence magnitudes, being the mitigation of the negative- and zero-sequence voltages activated in the event 6. The PI-OL controller and the sequence of events in the microgrid remain exactly the same. In this manner, it is possible to compare the existing symmetrical components approach with the proposed one based on the independent per-phase power control. The results are shown in Fig. 14, which represents the same magnitudes than Fig. 13 for comparison purposes. The only differences is that PI-CC represents the symmetric component voltages instead of phase voltages for evaluating the performance of negative and zero sequence voltage mitigation, and the virtual angular speed of the positive sequence.

The differences in the PI-CC performance from events 2 to 5 is due to its formulation based on the positive sequence magnitudes. Particularly, in the event 2, when the PI-CC is synchronizing, it can be noticed an increase of the neutral current above 10 A during a short period but with a reduced impact on the microgrid voltage. In this line, during event 5, connection of the unbalance load, the positive-sequence voltage increases which leads to a reactive power absorption

due to the action of its primary voltage controller. The main difference, as expected, is produced during the event 6, when the negative- and zero-sequence voltage reduction algorithm is activated in the PI-CC. It can be noticed that the controller practically balances the PCC 2 voltages ($V_- = 0.07$ V and $V_{o-} = 0.04$ V) by injecting a set of unbalanced powers, but different than those of the UPI-CC, as shown in Table V. Nevertheless, this local control action does not achieve the balancing effect on the GFM PI-OL which continues to share the power of the unbalanced load with the PI-CC. As a result, the PI-OL has a higher unbalanced current, leading to unbalanced voltages, as shown in the zoomed area, as well as higher oscillations in the power terms and angular speed imposed on the microgrid. Furthermore, this fact also leads to a lower microgrid angular speed compared to the UPI-CC.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper has addressed an independent per-phase power control for a 3P-4W virtual synchronous generator, with the aim of increasing the flexibility and controllability of inverter-based resources in grid-connected and islanded microgrids. The performance of the controller has been evaluated through CHIL tests in both steady-state, transient regimes and islanded microgrid scenario. The findings demonstrate the controller capability to independently regulate active and reactive power of the different phases under diverse operating scenarios. Moreover, the dynamics is consistent with that of a virtual synchronous generator implemented in each phase, being possible to provide an independent response to changes in the power references and inertia, even with different inertia constant values per phase. Furthermore, the proposal demonstrates that the controller is able to achieve an excellent decoupling between the different phase power terms both in permanent and transient regimes.

This functionality can be utilized by distribution system operators and in microgrids through existing inverter-based resources, enabling them to reduce voltage imbalances without requiring additional investments in new control assets. Furthermore, the proposed control would provide the LV network and microgrids with an inertial response and damping adapted to its inherently unbalanced nature. In this way, the per-phase power control with virtual synchronous generator capability would introduce new possibilities for control and flexibility in unbalanced systems. Particularly, the independent per-phase power control can be used in a straightforward manner along with centralized secondary controllers aimed at improving the overall system voltage imbalance. This strategy enhances the performance with respect to the local actions, usually based on symmetrical component approaches, aimed at reducing the imbalance in a particular node, as demonstrated in the analysis performed in the islanded microgrid.

Future work will consider control strategies that select appropriate active and reactive power references in both grid-connected and islanded microgrids with the goal of improving their overall operation. In addition, the performance of the per-phase virtual synchronous generator will be evaluated under large perturbations conditions such as balanced and unbalanced faults.

TABLE V

COMPARISON OF INJECTED POWERS DURING EVENT 6 WITH THE PROPOSED PER-PHASE VSG AND THE VSG BASED ON SYMMETRICAL COMPONENTS.

Magnitude	UPI-CC	PI-CC
P_a (kW)	3.014	2.494
P_b (kW)	1.055	0.804
P_c (kW)	0.985	0.713
P_+ (W)	5.055	3.862
Q_a (kvar)	1.984	1.320
Q_b (kvar)	0.065	-0.306
Q_c (kvar)	0.330	0.162
Q_+ (var)	2.380	1.633

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This publication is part of the project PID2021-124571OB-I00, funded by MICIU/AEI/ 10.13039/501100011033 and by ERDF/EU.

In addition, this work has been supported by the European Commission through the project SUNRISE under grant agreement 101079200 and Typhoon HIL, Inc.

REFERENCES

- [1] I. E. A. IEA, "Renewables 2024," tech. rep., 2024.
- [2] "Commission Regulation (EU) 2016/631 of 14 April 2016 establishing a network code on requirements for grid connection of generators," tech. rep., 2016.
- [3] Q.-C. Zhong and G. Weiss, "Synchronverters: Inverters that mimic synchronous generators," *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Electronics*, vol. 58, no. 4, pp. 1259–1267, 2011.
- [4] M. Sarwar, V. Ajjarapu, A. R. R. Matavalam, S. Roy, and H. N. V. Pico, "Short-term voltage stability improvement in power system through grid-forming hybrid pv plants," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, pp. 1–11, 2025.
- [5] A. THOMMESSEN and C. M. Hackl, "Virtual synchronous machine control for doubly fed induction machine-based wind energy conversion systems," *IEEE Open Journal of the Industrial Electronics Society*, vol. 5, pp. 264–301, 2024.
- [6] F. Wang, J. Xu, and G. Li, "A variable virtual impedance current limitation strategy of grid-forming energy storage-statcom," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 39, no. 6, pp. 3450–3461, 2024.
- [7] G. Shafique, J. Boukhenfouf, F. Gruson, F. Colas, and X. Guillaud, "Dc voltage control with grid-forming capability for enhancing stability of hvdc system," *Journal of Modern Power Systems and Clean Energy*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 66–78, 2025.
- [8] R. Musca, A. Vasile, and G. Zizzo, "Grid-forming converters. a critical review of pilot projects and demonstrators," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 165, p. 112551, 2022.
- [9] G. C. Kryonidis, K.-N. D. Malamaki, J. M. Mauricio, and C. S. Demoulias, "A new perspective on the synchronverter model," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 140, p. 108072, 2022.
- [10] S. Gupta and A. Shukla, "Enhancing stability of ac-dc microgrid cluster and reducing diesel dependency with bss," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 61, no. 3, pp. 4958–4970, 2025.
- [11] F. Sadeque, M. Gursoy, D. Sharma, and B. Mirafzal, "Autonomous control of inverters in microgrid," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 60, no. 3, pp. 4313–4323, 2024.
- [12] EN50160, "Voltage characteristics of electricity supplied by public electricity networks," tech. rep., 2023.
- [13] T. Gozel and L. Ochoa, *Deliverable 3.3 "(Updated) Performance evaluation of the monitored LV networks"*. United Kingdom: Electricity North West Limited (ENWL), July 2014.
- [14] M. R. Miveh, M. F. Rahmat, A. A. Ghadimi, and M. W. Mustafa, "Control techniques for three-phase four-leg voltage source inverters in autonomous microgrids: A review," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 54, pp. 1592–1610, 2016.
- [15] E. B. Avdiaj, S. D'Arco, L. Piegari, and J. A. Suul, "Negative sequence control for virtual synchronous machines under unbalanced conditions," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 10, no. 5, pp. 5670–5685, 2022.
- [16] Z. Zhu, W. Chen, and V. G. Monopoli, "Zero sequence voltage and current control in four-wire grids-fed by grid-forming inverters," *CSEE Journal of Power and Energy Systems*, vol. 9, no. 6, pp. 2272–2279, 2023.
- [17] B. Sharma, P. K. Pankaj, Y. Terriche, A. Saim, A. Shrestha, C.-L. Su, and J. M. Guerrero, "Power sharing in three-level npc inverter based three-phase four-wire islanding microgrids with unbalanced loads," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 20725–20740, 2023.
- [18] Á. Borrell, M. Velasco, M. Castilla, J. Miret, and R. Guzmán, "Collaborative voltage unbalance compensation in islanded ac microgrids with grid-forming inverters," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 37, no. 9, pp. 10499–10513, 2022.
- [19] A. Gastalver-Rubio, E. Romero-Ramos, and J. M. Maza-Ortega, "Improving the performance of low voltage networks by an optimized unbalance operation of three-phase distributed generators," *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 177504–177516, 2019.
- [20] Y.-C. Li, T.-W. Tsai, C.-J. Yang, Y.-M. Chen, and Y.-R. Chang, "Per-phase control strategy of the three-phase four-wire inverter," in *2018 International Power Electronics Conference (IPEC-Niigata 2018 -ECCE Asia)*, pp. 883–888, 2018.
- [21] A. M. Gross-Muresan, M. Majstorovic, F. J. Matas-Díaz, G. Dobric, M. Barragán-Villarejo, and J. M. Maza-Ortega, "Independent per-phase power control in four-leg grid-following voltage source converters," in *2024 International Symposium on Power Electronics, Electrical Drives, Automation and Motion (SPEEDAM)*, pp. 1105–1110, 2024.
- [22] J. Xu, H. Qian, S. Bian, Y. Hu, and S. Xie, "Comparative study of single-phase phase-locked loops for grid-connected inverters under non-ideal grid conditions," *CSEE Journal of Power and Energy Systems*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 155–164, 2022.
- [23] Y. Han, M. Luo, X. Zhao, J. M. Guerrero, and L. Xu, "Comparative performance evaluation of orthogonal-signal-generators-based single-phase pll algorithms—a survey," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 31, no. 5, pp. 3932–3944, 2016.
- [24] N. A. Ninad and L. A. C. Lopes, "Per-phase vector (dq) controlled three-phase grid-forming inverter for stand-alone systems," in *2011 IEEE International Symposium on Industrial Electronics*, pp. 1626–1631, 2011.
- [25] N. A. Ninad and L. A. C. Lopes, "Unbalanced operation of per-phase vector controlled four-leg grid forming inverter for stand-alone hybrid systems," in *IECON 2012 - 38th Annual Conference on IEEE Industrial Electronics Society*, pp. 3500–3505, 2012.
- [26] N. A. Ninad and L. Lopes, "Per-phase vector control strategy for a four-leg voltage source inverter operating with highly unbalanced loads in stand-alone hybrid systems," *International Journal of Electrical Power & Energy Systems*, vol. 55, pp. 449–459, 2014.
- [27] F. J. Matas-Díaz, A. Kontou, M. Barragán-Villarejo, P. Kotsampopoulos, J. M. Maza-Ortega, and N. Hatzigiorgiourou, "Assessment of control strategies for single-phase grid-forming voltage source converters," in *2023 International Conference on Smart Energy Systems and Technologies (SEST)*, pp. 1–6, 2023.
- [28] J. M. Maza-Ortega, M. Barragán-Villarejo, F. de Paula García-López, J. Jiménez, J. M. Mauricio, L. Alvarado-Barrios, and A. Gómez-Expósito, "A multi-platform lab for teaching and research in active distribution networks," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 32, no. 6, pp. 4861–4870, 2017.
- [29] F. Casado-Machado, J. L. Martínez-Ramos, M. Barragán-Villarejo, and J. M. Maza-Ortega, "Reduced reference frame transformation assessment in unbalanced three-phase four-wire systems," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 24591–24603, 2023.
- [30] A. G. Yepes, F. D. Freijedo, J. Doval-Gandoy, Ó. López, J. Malvar, and P. Fernandez-Comesaña, "Effects of discretization methods on the performance of resonant controllers," *IEEE Transactions on Power Electronics*, vol. 25, no. 7, pp. 1692–1712, 2010.
- [31] "Typhoon hil real-time hardware-in-the-loop (hil) simulation platform, typhoon hil control center release 2024.4, typhoon hil, inc. somerville, massachusetts, united states."
- [32] "Typhoon hil inc., "electric vehicle", typhoon hil documentation, https://www.typhoon-hil.com/documentation/typhoon-hil-application-notes/references/electric_vehicle.html."
- [33] F. J. Matas-Díaz, M. Barragán-Villarejo, and J. M. Maza-Ortega, "A systematic small-signal analysis procedure for improving synchronization stability of grid-forming virtual synchronous generators," *Journal of Modern Power Systems and Clean Energy*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 102–114, 2025.
- [34] F. J. Matas-Díaz, M. Barragán-Villarejo, J. M. Maza-Ortega, G. C. Kryonidis, K.-N. Malamaki, and C. S. Demoulias, "Active harmonic filtering with selective overcurrent limitation for grid-forming vsocs: Stability analysis and experimental validation," *IEEE Transactions on Industry Applications*, vol. 60, no. 3, pp. 4762–4775, 2024.
- [35] M. Ciobotaru, R. Teodorescu, and F. Blaabjerg, "A new single-phase pll structure based on second order generalized integrator," in *2006 37th IEEE Power Electronics Specialists Conference*, pp. 1–6, 2006.